

THE r -FIBONACCI POLYNOMIAL AND ITS COMPANION SEQUENCES LINKED WITH SOME CLASSICAL SEQUENCES

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Abstract

The aim of the present work is to provide some properties of the r -Fibonacci polynomial and its companion sequences. We present the Binet forms for both cases: distinct and multiple zeros of the characteristic polynomial. Then, we define their (p, q) -analogues and present the alternating sums of their terms using a matrix method. In addition, we extend the definition of the r -Fibonacci polynomial to include negative r values, we focus on the behavior of the resulting sequence, which is a solution of a recurrence relation, and establish its relationship with the generalized Padovan and Perrin numbers.

1. Introduction

The present paper is a continuation of our recent study [1] of the r -Fibonacci polynomial and its companion sequences. In [12], Raab introduced the r -Fibonacci bivariate polynomial sequence $(U_n^{(r)}(x, y))_n$ by the following recursion:

$$\begin{cases} U_0^{(r)} = 0, U_k^{(r)} = x^{k-1} \quad (1 \leq k \leq r), \\ U_{n+1}^{(r)} = xU_n^{(r)} + yU_{n-r}^{(r)} \quad (n \geq r), \end{cases}$$

where r is a positive integer, and x and y are two variables. Abbad et al. [1] defined a family of companion sequences $(V_n^{(r,s)})_{n \geq 0}$ indexed by s ($1 \leq s \leq r$) as follows:

$$\begin{cases} V_0^{(r,s)} = s + 1, V_k^{(r)} = x^k \ (1 \leq k \leq r), \\ V_{n+1}^{(r,s)} = xV_n^{(r,s)} + yV_{n-r}^{(r,s)} \ (n \geq r). \end{cases}$$

The sequence $(V_n^{(r,s)})$ is called the r -Lucas polynomial of type s . The sequences $(V_n^{(r,s)})_n$ and $(U_n^{(r)})_n$ are linked, for $n \geq r$, by the following relation:

$$V_n^{(r,s)} = U_{n+1}^{(r)} + syU_{n-r}^{(r)}. \tag{1}$$

For more details about the r -Fibonacci polynomial and its companion sequences, see [1]. This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the Binet formula for the r -Fibonacci polynomial and its companion sequences. Section 3 introduces (p, q) -analogues of these sequences. Section 4 employs a matrix method to evaluate the alternating sum of the r -Fibonacci polynomial and its companion sequences. Finally, the definition of the r -Fibonacci polynomial is extended to negative r values.

2. Binet Type Formulas

In this section, we present the Binet type formulas corresponding to the r -Fibonacci sequence and to the companion r -Lucas sequences.

Let $P(t) = t^{r+1} - xt^r - y = \prod_{j=1}^h (t - \alpha_j)^{r_j}$ be the characteristic polynomial of the sequences $(U_n^{(r)})_{n \geq 0}$ and $(V_n^{(r,s)})_{n \geq 0}$, where $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_h$ are the zeros of P and r_j is the multiplicity of α_j for $1 \leq j \leq h$ such that $\sum_{j=1}^h r_j = r + 1$. Raab [12] showed that $\alpha = rx/(r + 1)$ is a real multiple zero of P and that the greatest multiplicity of any real zero is two. DeGua's rule for identifying imaginary roots states that if $2m$ consecutive terms of an equation are missing, the equation has $2m$ imaginary roots. Similarly, when $2m - 1$ consecutive terms are missing, the equation has either $2m - 2$ or $2m$ imaginary roots, depending on whether the two terms between which the $2m - 1$ terms are missing have like or unlike signs. Consequently, we can deduce that the polynomial P has at most three real zeros. This is due to the presence of $(r - 1)$ consecutive missing terms in the expression of the linear recurrence relation, which implies that at least $(r - 2)$ of its zeros are imaginary. Additionally, α is a multiple zero of P if and only if the discriminant of P equals zero, leading to $y = (-1/r)(rx/(r + 1))^{r+1}$. As a result, the characteristic polynomial P can be split in the following way:

$$P(t) = (t - \alpha_1)(t - \alpha_2) \cdots (t - \alpha_{r+1}) \text{ if } y \neq (-1/r)(rx/(r + 1))^{r+1},$$

or

$$P(t) = (t - \alpha)^2 \tilde{P}(t) \text{ if } y = (-1/r)(rx/(r + 1))^{r+1}, \text{ where } \tilde{P}(\alpha) \neq 0.$$

Theorem 1. Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{r+1}$ be the zeros of the characteristic polynomial $P(t) = t^{r+1} - xt^r - y$ associated with $(U_n^{(r)})_{n \geq 0}$ and $(V_n^{(r,s)})_{n \geq 0}$. Then for $1 \leq s \leq r$, we have the following

(i) If $y \neq (-1/r)(rx/r + 1)^{r+1}$,

$$U_{n+1}^{(r)} = \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n+1}}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx} \quad \text{and} \quad V_n^{(r,s)} = \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \alpha_k^n \frac{(s+1)\alpha_k - sx}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx}.$$

(ii) If $y = (-1/r)(rx/r + 1)^{r+1}$,

$$U_{n+1}^{(r)} = \frac{\alpha^{n+r-1}}{\tilde{P}(\alpha)} \left((n+r) - \alpha \frac{\tilde{P}'(\alpha)}{\tilde{P}(\alpha)} \right) + \sum_{k=1, \alpha_k \neq \alpha}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n+1}}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx}$$

and

$$V_n^{(r,s)} = \frac{\alpha^{n+r-1}}{\tilde{P}(\alpha)} \left(n \left(\frac{r-s}{r} \right) + \left(r + \frac{s}{r} \right) - \alpha \left(\frac{r-s}{r} \right) \frac{\tilde{P}'(\alpha)}{\tilde{P}(\alpha)} \right) + \sum_{k=1, \alpha_k \neq \alpha}^{r+1} \alpha_k^n \frac{(s+1)\alpha_k - sx}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx}.$$

Proof. (i) As noted in [8], the general term of the sequence $(U_n^{(r)})_{n \geq 0}$ can be expressed as $U_{n+1}^{(r)} = \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} b_k \alpha_k^n$, where the b_k are rational numbers and the α_k are the zeros of the characteristic polynomial. This system of equations can be solved using Cramer's rule and the Vandermonde determinant. To find the coefficients b_k , we utilize the first $(r+1)$ terms of the sequence $(U_n^{(r)})$ and the symmetric functions of the zeros of the characteristic polynomial. The result is:

$$b_k = \frac{\alpha_k^r}{(\alpha_k - \alpha_1)(\alpha_k - \alpha_2) \cdots (\alpha_k - \alpha_{k-1})(\alpha_k - \alpha_{k+1}) \cdots (\alpha_k - \alpha_{r+1})} = \frac{\alpha_k^r}{\prod_{j \neq k} (\alpha_k - \alpha_j)}.$$

On the other hand, we notice that

$$P(t) = t^{r+1} - xt^r - y = (t - \alpha_1)(t - \alpha_2) \cdots (t - \alpha_{r+1}).$$

Then for $1 \leq k \leq r+1$, we have

$$P'(\alpha_k) = (r+1)\alpha_k^r - rx\alpha_k^{r-1} = \prod_{j \neq k} (\alpha_k - \alpha_j),$$

which gives

$$b_k = \frac{\alpha_k^r}{(r+1)\alpha_k^r - rx\alpha_k^{r-1}} = \frac{\alpha_k^r}{\alpha_k^{r-1}((r+1)\alpha_k - rx)} = \frac{\alpha_k}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx}.$$

Thus

$$U_{n+1}^{(r)} = \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} b_k \alpha_k^n = \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n+1}}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx}.$$

Now, we determine the Binet type formula for the sequence of polynomials $(V_n^{(r,s)})_{n \geq 0}$. Using Equation (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} V_n^{(r,s)} &= U_{n+1}^{(r)} + syU_{n-r}^{(r)} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n+1}}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx} + sy \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n-r}}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n-r}(\alpha_k^{r+1} + sy)}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, since $y = \alpha_k^{r+1} - x\alpha_k^r$, it follows that

$$V_n^{(r,s)} = \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n-r}((s+1)\alpha_k^{r+1} - sx\alpha_k^r)}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx} = \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \alpha_k^n \frac{(s+1)\alpha_k - sx}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx}.$$

(ii) Assuming that P has a multiple zero (let $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha$) and using the same technique as in (i), we have

$$\begin{aligned} U_{n+1}^{(r)} &= \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} b_k \alpha_k^n = b_1 \alpha_1^n + b_2 \alpha_2^n + \sum_{k=3}^{r+1} b_k \alpha_k^n \\ &= \frac{\alpha_1^{n+r}}{(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)\tilde{P}(\alpha_1)} + \frac{\alpha_2^{n+r}}{(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)\tilde{P}(\alpha_2)} \\ &\quad + \sum_{k=3}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n+r}}{(\alpha_k - \alpha_1)(\alpha_k - \alpha_2) \cdots (\alpha_k - \alpha_{k-1})(\alpha_k - \alpha_{k+1}) \cdots (\alpha_k - \alpha_{r+1})} \\ &= \frac{\alpha_1^{n+r}}{(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)\tilde{P}(\alpha_1)} - \frac{\alpha_2^{n+r}}{(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)\tilde{P}(\alpha_2)} + \sum_{\alpha_k \neq \alpha}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n+1}}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx} \\ &= \frac{1}{\tilde{P}(\alpha_1)} \left[\frac{\alpha_1^{n+r} - \alpha_2^{n+r}}{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2} - \left(\frac{\tilde{P}(\alpha_1)}{\tilde{P}(\alpha_2)} - 1 \right) \frac{\alpha_2^{n+r}}{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2} \right] + \sum_{\alpha_k \neq \alpha}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n+1}}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx} \\ &= \frac{1}{\tilde{P}(\alpha_1)} \left[\frac{\alpha_1^{n+r} - \alpha_2^{n+r}}{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2} - \left(\frac{\tilde{P}(\alpha_1) - \tilde{P}(\alpha_2)}{\alpha_1 - \alpha_2} \right) \frac{\alpha_2^{n+r}}{\tilde{P}(\alpha_2)} \right] + \sum_{\alpha_k \neq \alpha}^{r+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n+1}}{(r+1)\alpha_k - rx}. \end{aligned}$$

To end the proof, let α_2 tend to $\alpha_1 = \alpha$. For the companion sequences $(V_n^{(r,s)})_{n \geq 0}$, we apply Equation (1) with $y = -\frac{\alpha^{r+1}}{r}$. \square

3. The (p, q) -Analogue of the r -Fibonacci Polynomial and Its Companion Sequences

For $p, q \in \mathbb{R}$, the (p, q) -numbers are defined as:

$$[n]_{p,q} := p^{n-1} + p^{n-2}q + p^{n-2}q^2 + \dots + pq^{n-2} + q^{n-1} = \frac{p^n - q^n}{p - q},$$

$$[n]_{p,q}! := [1]_{p,q}[2]_{p,q} \cdots [n]_{p,q}.$$

Also, we have

$$[n]_{p,q} = p^{n-k}[k]_{p,q} + q^k[n - k]_{p,q},$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} n \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} = \frac{[n]_{p,q}!}{[k]_{p,q}![n - k]_{p,q}!},$$

and

$$\begin{bmatrix} n \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} = p^k \begin{bmatrix} n - 1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} + q^{n-k} \begin{bmatrix} n - 1 \\ k - 1 \end{bmatrix}_{p,q}, \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} n \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} = q^k \begin{bmatrix} n - 1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} + p^{n-k} \begin{bmatrix} n - 1 \\ k - 1 \end{bmatrix}_{p,q}. \tag{3}$$

The theory of (p, q) -calculus has been studied by many mathematicians. Corcino [11] studied the (p, q) -extension of the binomial coefficients and derived some properties similar to those of ordinary and q -binomial coefficients. In [3], Bazeniari et al. gave an interpretation of generalized binomial coefficients and their (p, q) -analogue using a new type of symmetric function. According to Ahmia and Belbachir [2], the log-convexity is preserved under the (p, q) -binomial transformation. In this section, we propose the (p, q) -analogue of the r -Fibonacci polynomial and its companion sequences associated with the unified approach of Cigler and Carlitz [7, 10]. Belbachir et al. [5] introduced the generalized q -analogue of r -Fibonacci polynomials $\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(z, m)$, which is a unified approach of those of Carlitz and Cigler [7, 10]. They define

$$\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(z, m) := \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} q^{\binom{k+1}{2} + m\binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n - rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_q z^k,$$

with $\mathbf{U}_0^{(r)}(z, m) = 0$. These polynomials satisfy the following recurrence formulas:

$$\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(z, m) = \mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(qz, m) + qz\mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(zq^{m+1}, m)$$

and

$$\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(z, m) = \mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(z, m) + q^{n-r}z\mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(zq^{m-r}, m).$$

Also, Benmezai proposed the (p, q) -analogue of the r -Fibonacci polynomial associated with the Cigler approach [6]. Inspired by the (p, q) -binomial definition given in [11], we propose the following definition for the (p, q) -analogue of r -Fibonacci polynomials.

Definition 1. For all $n \geq 0$, the (p, q) -analogue of the r -Fibonacci polynomial is defined as

$$\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x, y, p, q, m) := \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n+1-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}+m\binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k,$$

with $\mathbf{U}_0^{(r)} = 0$ and $\mathbf{U}_j^{(r)} = p^{\binom{j+1}{2}} x^{j-1}$ for $1 \leq j \leq r$.

By setting $p = 1$, we derive some particular cases of the (p, q) -analogue of the r -Fibonacci polynomial. This includes the q -analogue presented in [5] and the q -analogue introduced by Cigler in [9], where $r = 1$ and $m = 0$.

Theorem 2. *The (p, q) -analogue of the r -Fibonacci polynomials satisfy the following recurrence formulas:*

$$\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x, y, p, q, m) = px\mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(px, qy, p, q, m) + qy\mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(px, q^{m+1}y, p, q, m) \quad (4)$$

and

$$\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x, y, p, q, m) = px\mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(px, py, p, q, m) + qy\mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(qx, q^{m+1}y, p, q, m). \quad (5)$$

Proof. We use Equation (2) to prove the first identity. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x, y, p, q, m) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n+1-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}+m\binom{k}{2}} \\ & \quad \times \left(q^k \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} + p^{n-(r+1)k} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k-1 \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} \right) x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k \\ &= px \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}+m\binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} (px)^{n-(r+1)k-1} (qy)^k \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n+1-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}+m\binom{k}{2}} p^{n-(r+1)k} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k-1 \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k \\
 = & px \mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(px, qy, p, q, m) + \sum_{k=1}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n+1-(r+1)(k+1)}{2}} q^{\binom{k+2}{2}+m\binom{k+1}{2}} p^{n-(r+1)(k+1)} \\
 & \times \begin{bmatrix} n-r(k+1)-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)(k+1)} y^{k+1} \\
 = & px \mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(px, qy, p, q, m) + qy \sum_{k=1}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-r-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}+m\binom{k}{2}} \\
 & \times \begin{bmatrix} n-r-1-rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} (px)^{n-r-1-(r+1)k} (q^{m+1}y)^k \\
 = & px \mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(px, qy, p, q, m) + qy \mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(px, q^{m+1}y, p, q, m).
 \end{aligned}$$

Now we use Equation (3) to prove the second identity. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x, y, p, q, m) \\
 = & \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n+1-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}+m\binom{k}{2}} \\
 & \times \left(p^k \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} + q^{n-(r+1)k} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k-1 \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} \right) x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k \\
 = & px \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}+m\binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} (px)^{n-(r+1)k-1} (py)^k \\
 & + \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n+1-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}+m\binom{k}{2}} q^{n-(r+1)k} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k-1 \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k, \\
 = & px \mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(px, py, p, q, m) + \sum_{k=1}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n+1-(r+1)(k+1)}{2}} q^{\binom{k+2}{2}+m\binom{k+1}{2}} q^{n-(r+1)(k+1)} \\
 & \times \begin{bmatrix} n-r(k+1)-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)(k+1)} y^{k+1} \\
 = & px \mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(px, py, p, q, m) + qy \sum_{k=1}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-r-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}+m\binom{k}{2}} \\
 & \times \begin{bmatrix} n-r-1-rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} (qx)^{n-r-1-(r+1)k} (q^{m+1}y)^k \\
 = & px \mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(px, py, p, q, m) + qy \mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(qx, q^{m+1}y, p, q, m).
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Definition 2. Let r and s be positive integers such that $1 \leq s \leq r$. For $n \geq 0$, we define the (p, q) -analogue of the r -Lucas polynomials of type s of the *first kind* and the *second kind*, respectively, as follows:

$$\mathbf{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) := \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{m+1}{2} \binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} \times \left(1 + \frac{sp^{n-(r+1)k} [k]_{p,q}}{[n-rk]_{p,q}} \right) x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k$$

and

$$\mathbb{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) := \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2} + m \binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} \times p^{-k} \left(1 + \frac{sq^{(n-(r+1)k)} [k]_{p,q}}{[n-rk]_{p,q}} \right) x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k,$$

with $\mathbf{V}_0^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = \mathbb{V}_0^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = s + 1$.

Remark 1. Note that for $p = 1$, we obtain the q -analogue of the r -Lucas polynomial of type s ; see [1].

Let us now establish some links with the initial r -Fibonacci polynomial.

Theorem 3. For positive integers r and s , the polynomials $\mathbf{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m)$ and $\mathbb{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m)$ satisfy the following recursions:

1. (Expression of $V_n^{(r,s)}$'s in terms of $\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}$ and $\mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}$ without weight)

$$\mathbf{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = \mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x/p, y/q, p, q, m) + sy\mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(x, yq^m, p, q, m),$$

$$\mathbb{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = \mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x/p, y/p, p, q, m) + sy(q/p)^{n-r}\mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(x, yq^m, p, q, m);$$

2. (Expression of $V_n^{(r,s)}$'s in terms of $\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}$ and $\mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}$ weighted by s)

$$\mathbf{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = (s + 1)\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x/p, y/q, p, q, m) - sx\mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(x, y, p, q, m),$$

$$\mathbb{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = (s + 1)\mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x/p, y/p, p, q, m) - sx\mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(x, y, p, q, m);$$

3. (Expression of $V_n^{(r,s)}$'s in terms of $\mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}$ and $\mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}$)

$$\mathbf{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = x\mathbf{U}_n(x, y, p, q, m) + (1 + s)y\mathbf{U}_{n-r}(x, yq^m, p, q, m),$$

$$\mathbb{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = x\mathbf{U}_n^{(r)}(x, y, p, q, m) + (1 + s)(q/p)^{n-r}y\mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(x, yq^m, p, q, m).$$

Proof. We prove the first two relations. The other identities are proved in the same way. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathbf{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k}{2}(m+1)} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k \\
 &\quad + s \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-(r+1)k}{2} + (n-(r+1)k)} q^{\binom{k}{2}(m+1)} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k-1 \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n+1-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2} + m \binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} (x/p)^{n-(r+1)k} (y/q)^k \\
 &\quad + s \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n+1-(r+1)(k+1)}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2}(m+1)} \begin{bmatrix} n-r(k+1)-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)(k+1)} y^{k+1} \\
 &= \mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x/p, y/q, p, q, m) \\
 &\quad + sy \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-r-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2} + m \binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n-r-1-rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-r-1-rk} (q^m y)^k \\
 &= \mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x/p, y/q, p, q, m) + sy \mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(x, q^m y, p, q, m).
 \end{aligned}$$

For the second identity, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathbf{V}_n^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2} + m \binom{k}{2}} p^{-k} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k \\
 &\quad + s \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2} + m \binom{k}{2}} p^{-k} q^{n-(r+1)k} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k-1 \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n+1-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2} + m \binom{k}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} (x/p)^{n-(r+1)k} (y/p)^k \\
 &\quad + s \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2} + m \binom{k}{2}} p^{-k} q^{n-(r+1)k} \begin{bmatrix} n-rk-1 \\ k-1 \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-(r+1)k} y^k \\
 &= \mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x/p, y/p, p, q, m) + sy \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-r-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2} + m \binom{k}{2}} q^{(m-r)k+n-r} \\
 &\quad \times p^{-n+r(k+1)} \begin{bmatrix} n-r(k+1)-1 \\ k \end{bmatrix}_{p,q} x^{n-r-1-(r+1)k} y^k
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x/p, y/p, p, q, m) + sy(q/p)^{n-r} \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor} p^{\binom{n-r-(r+1)k}{2}} q^{\binom{k+1}{2} + m \binom{k}{2}} \\
 &\quad \times \left[\begin{matrix} n-r-1-rk \\ k \end{matrix} \right]_{p,q} x^{n-r-1-(r+1)k} (p^r q^{m-r} y)^k \\
 &= \mathbf{U}_{n+1}^{(r)}(x/p, y/p, p, q, m) + sy(q/p)^{n-r} \mathbf{U}_{n-r}^{(r)}(x, yp^r q^{m-r}, p, q, m).
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Using the previous identities, we show that the (p, q) -analogue of the r -Lucas polynomials of type s of the first and second kind satisfy the same recurrence relations as the (p, q) -analogue of the r -Fibonacci polynomial given in Relations (4) and (5).

Corollary 1. *The (p, q) -analogue of the r -Lucas polynomial of type s of the first and second kind satisfy the following recurrences, respectively:*

$$\mathbf{V}_{n+1}^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = px \mathbf{V}_n^{(r,s)}(px, qy, p, q, m) + qy \mathbf{V}_{n-r}^{(r,s)}(px, q^{m+1}y, p, q, m)$$

and

$$\mathbb{V}_{n+1}^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = px \mathbb{V}_n^{(r,s)}(px, py, p, q, m) + qy \mathbb{V}_{n-r}^{(r,s)}(qx, q^{m+1}y, p, q, m),$$

with $\mathbf{V}_0^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = \mathbb{V}_0^{(r,s)}(x, y, p, q, m) = s + 1$.

4. The Alternating Sum of Finite Terms of the r -Fibonacci Polynomial and the Related Companion Sequences

To derive an explicit formula for the alternating sum of the r -Fibonacci polynomial terms and its companion sequences, we introduce a new sequence $\xi_n^{(r)} = m^{n-1} U_n^{(r)}$, where m is a positive integer. This sequence satisfies the recurrence relation

$$\xi_{n+1}^{(r)} = mx \xi_n^{(r)} + m^{r+1} y \xi_{n-r}^{(r)},$$

with initial conditions $\xi_0^{(r)} = 0, \xi_k^{(r)} = (mx)^{k-1}$ ($1 \leq k \leq r$). Let $A_r(x, y)$ be the companion matrix of order $(r + 1)$ associated with $\xi_n^{(r)}$:

$$A_r(x, y) := \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & m^{r+1}y \\ 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & mx \end{pmatrix},$$

and its n -power

$$A_r^n(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} m^{r+1}y\xi_{n-r}^{(r)} & y\xi_{n-r+1}^{(r)} & \cdots & m^{r+1}y\xi_{n-1}^{(r)} & m^{r+1}y\xi_n^{(r)} \\ m^{r+1}y\xi_{n-r-1}^{(r)} & y\xi_{n-r}^{(r)} & \cdots & m^{r+1}y\xi_{n-2}^{(r)} & m^{r+1}y\xi_{n-1}^{(r)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ m^{r+1}y\xi_{n-2r+1}^{(r)} & y\xi_{n-2r+2}^{(r)} & \cdots & m^{r+1}y\xi_{n-r}^{(r)} & m^{r+1}y\xi_{n-r+1}^{(r)} \\ \xi_{n-r+1}^{(r)} & \xi_{n-r+2}^{(r)} & \cdots & \xi_n^{(r)} & \xi_{n+1}^{(r)} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Using a matrix approach, we compute $S_n^{(r)}(m)$, the sum of the terms of the sequence $(\xi_n^{(r)})_n$, given by

$$S_n^{(r)}(m) = \sum_{j=1}^n \xi_j^{(r)}.$$

The following result is a generalization of Theorem 4 in [1]. The proof follows a similar approach.

Theorem 4. *Let $S_n^{(r)}(m)$ be the sum of the first n terms of the sequence $(\xi_k^{(r)})$, and let $P(t) = t^{r+1} - mx t^r - m^{r+1}y$ be its characteristic polynomial such that $P(1) \neq 0$. Then*

$$S_n^{(r)}(m) = \frac{1}{1 - mx - m^{r+1}y} (1 - \xi_{n+1}^{(r)} - m^{r+1}y \sum_{j=1}^r \xi_{n-r+j}^{(r)}). \tag{6}$$

Corollary 2 ([1, Theorem 4]). *The sum of the terms of $(U_n^{(r)}(x, y))_n$ is given by*

$$S_n^{(r)}(1) = \frac{1}{1 - x - y} (1 - U_{n+1}^{(r)} - y \sum_{j=1}^r U_{n-r+j}^{(r)}).$$

Corollary 3. *The alternating sum of the terms of $(U_n^{(r)}(x, y))_n$ is given by*

$$S_n^{(r)}(-1) = \frac{1}{1 + x + (-1)^r y} (1 - (-1)^n U_{n+1}^{(r)} + (-1)^r y \sum_{j=1}^r (-1)^{n-r+j-1} U_{n-r+j}^{(r)}).$$

Example 1. For $r = 1$ and $(x, y) = (1, 1)$, we obtain the alternating sum of Fibonacci numbers $(F_n)_{n \geq 0}$ (A000045 in the OEIS),

$$\sum_{j=1}^n (-1)^{j-1} F_j = 1 - (-1)^n F_{n-1}.$$

Example 2. For $r = 1$ and $(x, y) = (2, 1)$, the sequence $(U_n^{(r)})$ reduces to the usual Pell sequence $(P_n)_{n \geq 0}$ (A000129 in the OEIS). We have

$$\sum_{j=1}^n (-1)^{j-1} P_j = \frac{1}{2} (1 + (-1)^{n-1} (P_{n+1} - P_n)).$$

Example 3. For $r = 2$ and $(x, y) = (1, 1)$, we obtain the 2-Fibonacci numbers $(T_n)_{n \geq 0}$ (A000930 in the OEIS), which satisfy the recursion $T_{n+1} = T_n + T_{n-2}$ with $T_0 = 0, T_1 = T_2 = 1$. Then

$$\sum_{j=1}^n T_j = (T_{n+3} - 1) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{j=1}^n (-1)^{j-1} T_j = \frac{1}{3}(1 - (-1)^n(T_{n+1} + T_{n-3})).$$

Now, we derive the expression for the sum of the terms of the companion sequences $(\eta_n^{(r,s)})$ of $(\xi_n^{(r)})$ defined by

$$S_n^{(r,s)}(m) = \sum_{j=1}^n \eta_j^{(r,s)} = \sum_{j=1}^n m^j V_j^{(r,s)}.$$

Theorem 5. Let $S_n^{(r,s)}(m)$ be the sum of the first n terms of $(\eta_k^{(r,s)})$, and let $P(t) = t^{r+1} - mx t^r - m^{r+1} y$ be the corresponding characteristic polynomial such that $P(1) \neq 0$. Then

$$S_n^{(r,s)}(m) = \frac{1}{1 - mx - m^{r+1}y} (1 + sm^{r+1}y - \eta_{n+1}^{(r,s)} - m^{r+1}y \sum_{j=1}^r \eta_{n-r+j}^{(r,s)}) - 1.$$

Proof. According to Equation (1), the companion sequences $(\eta_n^{(r,s)})$ satisfy the relation

$$\eta_n^{(r,s)} = \xi_{n+1}^{(r)} + sm^{r+1}y \xi_{n-r}^{(r)}.$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=r}^n \eta_j^{(r,s)} &= \sum_{j=r}^n (\xi_{j+1}^{(r)} + sm^{r+1}y \xi_{j-r}^{(r)}) \\ &= \sum_{j=r+1}^{n+1} \xi_j^{(r)} + sm^{r+1}y \sum_{j=1}^{n-r} \xi_j^{(r)} \\ &= S_{n+1}^{(r)}(m) - \sum_{j=1}^r \xi_j^{(r)} + sm^{r+1}y S_{n-r}^{(r)}(m). \end{aligned}$$

Since $\sum_{j=1}^r \xi_j^{(r)} = \sum_{j=1}^r (mx)^{j-1} = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} (mx)^j = 1 + \sum_{j=1}^{r-1} \eta_j^{(r,s)}$, using Equation (6), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^n \eta_j^{(r,s)} + 1 &= \frac{1}{1 - mx - m^{r+1}y} (1 - \xi_{n+2}^{(r)} - m^{r+1}y \sum_{j=1}^r \xi_{n-r+j+1}^{(r)}) \\ &\quad + sy \frac{1}{1 - mx - m^{r+1}y} (1 - \xi_{n-r+1}^{(r)} - m^{r+1}y \sum_{j=1}^r \xi_{n-2r+j}^{(r)}) \\ &= \frac{1 + sm^{r+1}y - \eta_{n+1}^{(r,s)} - m^{r+1}y \sum_{j=1}^r \eta_{n-r+j}^{(r,s)}}{1 - mx - m^{r+1}y}. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we have

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \eta_j^{(r,s)} = \frac{1 + sm^{r+1}y - \eta_{n+1}^{(r,s)} - m^{r+1}y \sum_{j=1}^r \eta_{n-r+j}^{(r,s)}}{1 - mx - m^{r+1}y} - 1.$$

□

Theorem 5 allows us to evaluate the alternating sum for the terms of the companion sequences of the r -Fibonacci polynomial.

Corollary 4 ([1, Theorem 5]). *For any integer $n \geq 1$, we have*

$$\sum_{j=1}^n V_j^{(r,s)} = S_n^{(r,s)}(1) = \frac{1 + sy - V_{n+1}^{(r,s)} - y \sum_{j=1}^r V_{n-r+j}^{(r,s)}}{1 - x - y} - 1.$$

Corollary 5. *The alternating sum of the terms of $(V_n^{(r,s)}(x, y))_n$ is given by*

$$\sum_{j=1}^n (-1)^j V_j^{(r,s)} = \frac{1 - (-1)^r sy + (-1)^n V_{n+1}^{(r,s)} + (-1)^r y \sum_{j=1}^r (-1)^{n-r+j} V_{n-r+j}^{(r,s)}}{1 + x + (-1)^r y} - 1.$$

Example 4. For $(r, s) = (1, 1)$ and $(x, y) = (1, 1)$, we obtain the finite alternating sum of the Lucas numbers (A000032 in the OEIS), and

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^k L_k = 1 + (-1)^n L_{n-1}.$$

Example 5. For $(r, s) = (2, 1)$ and $(x, y) = (1, 1)$, we obtain $(T_n^{(2,1)})_{n \geq 0}$, the 2-Fibonacci-Lucas numbers of type 1, and we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n T_k^{(2,1)} = T_{n+3}^{(2,1)} - 3 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^k T_k^{(2,1)} = \frac{1}{3}((-1)^n (T_{n+1}^{(2,1)} + T_{n-3}^{(2,1)}) - 1).$$

Example 6. For $(r, s) = (2, 2)$ and $(x, y) = (1, 1)$, we get $(T_n^{(2,2)})_{n \geq 0}$, the 2-Fibonacci-Lucas numbers of type 2, and we find

$$\sum_{k=1}^n T_k^{(2,2)} = T_{n+3}^{(2,2)} - 4 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^k T_k^{(2,2)} = \frac{1}{3}(-1 + (-1)^n (T_{n+1}^{(2,1)} + T_{n-3}^{(2,1)}) - 1).$$

5. Extension of the r -Fibonacci Polynomial to Negative r Values

Our purpose in this section is to expand the definition of the r -Fibonacci polynomial to include negative values of r . We establish an explicit formula for the general term of this extended polynomial sequence. Subsequently, we determine its generating function and provide Binet-like formulae. We consider x and y to be invertible elements within a commutative unitary ring \mathcal{A} .

Definition 3. For any integer $r \geq 2$, we define the $(-r)$ -Fibonacci bivariate polynomial sequence $(U_n^{(-r)}(x, y))_n$ by the following recursion:

$$\begin{cases} U_0^{(-r)} = 0, U_1^{(-r)} = 1, U_2^{(-r)} = \dots = U_r^{(-r)} = 0, \\ U_{n+1}^{(-r)} = y^{-1}U_{n-r+1}^{(-r)} - y^{-1}xU_{n-r}^{(-r)} \quad (n \geq r). \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

Theorem 6. Let r be a nonnegative integer, and x, y two elements of a commutative unitary ring \mathcal{A} . We suppose that x and y are reversible in \mathcal{A} . Then for $n \geq 1$, we have

$$U_{n+1}^{(-r)} = \sum_k \binom{k}{n-rk} y^{-k} (-x)^{n-rk},$$

or

$$U_{n+1}^{(-r)} = \sum_k \binom{(n-k)/r}{k} y^{-(n-k)/r} (-x)^k.$$

The first sum is confined to integer values of k ranging from $\lfloor n/(r+1) \rfloor$ to $\lfloor n/r \rfloor$. The second sum is limited to integer k values between 0 and $\lfloor n/r \rfloor$ such that r divides $(n-k)$.

Proof. Using Theorem 3 given in [4], we consider the sequence $(U_n^{(-r)})_n$ given by $U_n^{(-r)} = y^{-1}U_{n-r}^{(-r)} - y^{-1}xU_{n-r-1}^{(-r)}$ with $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_{r-1} = 0$, $a_r = y^{-1}$ and $a_{r+1} = -xy^{-1}$. Then, for $n \geq -r$, we have

$$y_n^{(-r)} = \sum_{ri+(r+1)j=n} \binom{i+j}{j} (y^{-1})^i (-xy^{-1})^j = \sum_{r(i+j)+j=n} \binom{i+j}{j} (y^{-1})^{i+j} (-x)^j.$$

Letting $i + j = k$, we obtain

$$y_n^{(-r)} = \sum_k^{\lfloor n/r \rfloor} \binom{k}{n-rk} (-x)^{n-rk} (y^{-1})^k,$$

with initial conditions, $U_{-j}^{(-r)} = 0$ for $0 \leq j \leq r-1$, and $U_{-r}^{(-r)} = -x^{-1}y$. On the other hand, let $(\lambda_j)_{0 \leq j \leq r}$ be the sequence defined by $\lambda_j = \sum_{k=0}^{r-j} a_k U_{k+j}^{(-r)}$, with

$a_0 = -1$. We have $\lambda_j = 0$ for $1 \leq j \leq r - 1$, $\lambda_0 = x^{-1}$ and $\lambda_r = -x^{-1}y$. The sequence $(U_n^{(-r)})_n$ can be expressed as

$$U_n^{(-r)} = \sum_{j=0}^r \lambda_j y_{n+j}^{(-r)} = \lambda_0 y_n^{(-r)} + \lambda_r y_{n+r}^{(-r)} = \sum_k^{\lfloor n/r \rfloor} \binom{k}{n-1-rk} (-x)^{n-1-rk} (y^{-1})^k.$$

Setting $n - rk = k'$, the second sum is easily obtained. □

Remark 2. The companion matrix of the $(-r)$ -Fibonacci sequence of order $(r + 1)$ is given as follows:

$$B_r(x, y) := \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \cdots & y^{-1} & -xy^{-1} \\ 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

By an inductive argument and using Equation (7), we get its n th power

$$B_r^n(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} U_{n+1}^{(-r)} & U_{n+2}^{(-r)} & \cdots & U_{n+r}^{(-r)} & -xy^{-1}U_n^{(-r)} \\ U_n^{(-r)} & U_{n+1}^{(-r)} & \cdots & U_{n+r-1}^{(-r)} & -xy^{-1}U_{n-1}^{(-r)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ U_{n-r+2}^{(-r)} & U_{n-r+3}^{(-r)} & \cdots & U_{n+1}^{(-r)} & -xy^{-1}U_{n-r+1}^{(-r)} \\ U_{n-r+1}^{(-r)} & U_{n-r+2}^{(-r)} & \cdots & U_n^{(-r)} & -xy^{-1}U_{n-r}^{(-r)} \end{pmatrix}.$$

The sequence $(U_n^{(-r)})_n$ possesses combinatorial properties. It immediately follows that

$$U_{n+m}^{(-r)} = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} U_{n+j}^{(-r)} U_{m+1-j}^{(-r)} - xy^{-1} U_{n-1}^{(-r)} U_{m-r+1}^{(-r)}.$$

Setting $n = m$, we obtain

$$U_{2n}^{(-r)} = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} U_{n+j}^{(-r)} U_{n+1-j}^{(-r)} - xy^{-1} U_{n-1}^{(-r)} U_{n-r+1}^{(-r)}.$$

Specifically, we find the following identity for Padovan numbers by entering $r = 2$ and $(x, y) = (-1, 1)$,

$$P_{2n} = 2P_n P_{n+1} + (P_{n-1})^2.$$

Now, we define the companion sequence associated with the $(-r)$ -Fibonacci polynomial.

Definition 4. For any integer $r \geq 2$, we define the companion sequence related to $(U_n^{(-r)})_n$ by the following recurrence relation:

$$\begin{cases} V_0^{(-r)} = r + 1, V_1^{(-r)} = \dots = V_{r-1}^{(-r)} = 0, V_r^{(-r)} = ry^{-1}, \\ V_{n+1}^{(-r)} = y^{-1}V_{n-r+1}^{(-r)} - y^{-1}xV_{n-r}^{(-r)}, (n \geq r). \end{cases}$$

The $(-r)$ -Fibonacci polynomial and its companion sequence satisfy a similar identity to (1). The following proposition gives an explicit form for $V_n^{(-r)}$ in terms of r and $U_n^{(-r)}$.

Proposition 1. Let $r \geq 2$ be an integer and x, y be reversible elements of a commutative unitary ring \mathcal{A} . For $n \geq r$, we have

$$V_n^{(-r)} = rU_{n+1}^{(-r)} - xy^{-1}U_{n-r}^{(-r)}. \tag{8}$$

Proof. We consider the sequence $(V_n^{(-r)})$ given by the recurrence relation

$$V_n^{(-r)} = y^{-1}V_{n-r}^{(-r)} - y^{-1}xV_{n-r-1}^{(-r)}.$$

Applying Theorem 3 in [4], for $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_{r-1} = 0$, $a_r = y^{-1}$ and $a_{r+1} = -xy^{-1}$, we get $V_{-j}^{(-r)} = (x^{-j})$ for $1 \leq j \leq r$ and $V_0^{(-r)} = r + 1$. Thus, the sequence $(\lambda_j)_{0 \leq j \leq r}$ becomes

$$\lambda_j = - \sum_{k=0}^{r-j} a_k V_{k+j}^{(-r)},$$

with $a_0 = -1$. So, $\lambda_0 = r + 1 - y^{-1}(x^{-1})^r$ and $\lambda_j = x^{-j}$ for $1 \leq j \leq r$. Finally, we get

$$\begin{aligned} V_n^{(-r)} &= \lambda_0 U_{n+1}^{(-r)} + \lambda_1 U_{n+2}^{(-r)} + \dots + \lambda_r U_{n+r+1}^{(-r)} \\ &= rU_{n+1}^{(-r)} + U_{n+1}^{(-r)} - y^{-1}U_{n-r+1}^{(-r)} \\ &= rU_{n+1}^{(-r)} - y^{-1}xU_{n-r}^{(-r)}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 7. For $n \geq 1$, the sequence $(V_n^{(-r)})_{n \geq 1}$ satisfies the following two equivalent identities:

$$V_n^{(-r)} = \sum_k \frac{n}{n-rk} \binom{k-1}{n-1-rk} y^{-k} (-x)^{n-rk} + ry^{-n/r} [r \mid n]$$

or

$$V_n^{(-r)} = \sum_k \frac{n}{k+1} \binom{(n-1-r-k)/r}{k} y^{-(n-1-k)/r} (-x)^{k+1} + ry^{-n/r} [r \mid n],$$

with $V_0^{(-r)} = r + 1$ and $[r \mid n] = 1$ for r dividing n and $[r \mid n] = 0$ otherwise. The first summation is restricted to integers $k \geq 0$ such that $\lfloor n/(r + 1) \rfloor \leq k \leq \lfloor n/r \rfloor$; the second summation is limited to integers $0 \leq k \leq \lfloor n/(r + 1) \rfloor - 1$ for which r divides $(n - k - 1)$.

Proof. The proof is done using Equation (8) and Theorem 6. □

We mention that for any integer $r \geq 2$, the $(-r)$ -Fibonacci polynomial $(U_n^{(-r)})_n$ and its companion sequence $(V_n^{(-r)})_n$ are linked with some classical sequences. There are many studies in the literature that concern the particular case $(x, y) = (-1, 1)$ that include Padovan numbers $(P_n)_{n \geq 0}$ (A000931 in the OEIS) and Perrin (Padovan-Lucas) numbers $(E_n)_{n \geq 0}$ (A001608 in the OEIS) for $r = 2$ (see for instance, [13] and references therein). We also have the sequences (A127838 and A050443 in the OEIS) for $r = 3$. In Table 1, we present a chart of these sequences for the first values of r .

Name	Sloane's code	First terms
$U_n^{(-2)}$	A000931	0, 1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 12, 16,...
$U_n^{(-3)}$	A127838	0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 2, 1, 1, 3, 3, 2, 4,...
$U_n^{(-4)}$	A127839	0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 0, 1, 2, 1, 0, 1, 3,...
$U_n^{(-5)}$	A127840	0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 2, 1, 0,...
$V_n^{(-2)}$	A001608	3, 0, 2, 3, 2, 5, 5, 7, 10, 12, 17, 22, 29, 39,...
$V_n^{(-3)}$	A050443	4, 0, 0, 3, 4, 0, 3, 7, 4, 3, 10, 11, 7, 13, 21,...
$V_n^{(-4)}$	A087935	5, 0, 0, 0, 4, 5, 0, 0, 4, 9, 5, 0, 4, 13, 14, 5, 4,...
$V_n^{(-5)}$	A087936	6, 0, 0, 0, 0, 5, 6, 0, 0, 0, 5, 11, 6, 0, 0, 5, 16,...

Table 1: The first terms of $(U_n^{(-r)})_n$ and $(V_n^{(-r)})_n$.

The sequences $(U_n^{(-r)}(x, y))_n$ and $(V_n^{(-r)}(x, y))_n$ are called the r -generalized Padovan and r -generalized Perrin numbers, respectively.

The generating functions of the $(-r)$ -Fibonacci sequence and its companion sequence are given by the following theorem.

Theorem 8. For $z \in \mathbb{C}$ the generating functions of $(U_n^{(-r)})_{n \geq 0}$ and $(V_n^{(-r)})_{n \geq 0}$ are given by

$$U(z) = \sum_{n \geq 0} U_{n+1}^{(-r)} z^n = \frac{1}{1 - y^{-1}z^r + xy^{-1}z^{r+1}}$$

and

$$V(z) = \sum_{n \geq 0} V_n^{(-r)} z^n = \frac{r + 1 - y^{-1}z^r}{1 - y^{-1}z^r + xy^{-1}z^{r+1}},$$

respectively.

Proof. Let $U(z) = U_1^{(-r)} + U_2^{(-r)}z + U_3^{(-r)}z^2 \dots$; then using Equation (7), we have

$$(1 - y^{-1}z^r + xy^{-1}z^{r+1})U(z) = U_1^{(-r)} \text{ and } U(z) = \frac{1}{1 - y^{-1}z^r + xy^{-1}z^{r+1}}.$$

Finally, the expression of $V(z)$ is obtained by Equation (8). □

5.1. Binet Formulae

In this subsection, we give the Binet formula associated with the $(-r)$ -Fibonacci sequence and its companion sequence. We start with the following result.

Lemma 1. *Let $P(t) = t^{r+1} - y^{-1}t + xy^{-1}$ be the characteristic polynomial of the sequence $(U_n^{(-r)})_n$. We suppose that $x \neq (\frac{r}{r+1})((r+1)y)^{-1/r}$. Then, the polynomial P has no multiple zeros.*

Proof. Suppose that $P(t) = 0$ has a multiple root β with $\beta \neq 0$. Then, we have $P(\beta) = \beta^{r+1} - y^{-1}\beta + xy^{-1} = 0$ and $P'(\beta) = (r+1)\beta^r - y^{-1} = 0$, so $\beta = (\frac{y^{-1}}{r+1})^{\frac{1}{r}}$. Hence $P(\beta) = (\frac{y^{-1}}{r+1})^{\frac{r+1}{r}} - y^{-1}(\frac{y^{-1}}{r+1})^{\frac{1}{r}} + xy^{-1} = 0$, which gives

$$x = (\frac{r}{r+1})((r+1)y)^{\frac{-1}{r}}.$$

□

Theorem 9. *Let $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{r+1}$ be the zeros of the characteristic polynomial associated with $(U_n^{(-r)})_{n \geq 0}$ such that $x \neq (\frac{r}{r+1})((r+1)y)^{-1/r}$. Then*

$$U_{n+1}^{(-r)} = \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{\beta_k^{n+r+1}}{r\beta_k^{r+1} - xy^{-1}} \quad \text{and} \quad V_n^{(-r)} = \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \beta_k^n.$$

Proof. Let $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{r+1}$ be the eigenvalues of the matrix $B_r(x, y)$ and $M_r(x, y)$ be the Vandermonde matrix given as follows:

$$M_r(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_1^r & \beta_2^r & \cdots & \beta_{r+1}^r \\ \beta_1^{r-1} & \beta_2^{r-1} & \cdots & \beta_{r+1}^{r-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \beta_1 & \beta_2 & \vdots & \beta_{r+1} \\ 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The eigenvalues of the matrix $B_r(x, y)$ are all distinct if we suppose the discriminant of the characteristic polynomial associated with $(U_n^{(-r)})_{n \geq 0}$ is different from zero,

so the matrix $B_r(x, y)$ is diagonalizable and the relation $B_r(x, y) \times M_r(x, y) = M_r(x, y) \times D$ is satisfied, where $D = \text{Diag}(\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{r+1})$. Then,

$$M_r^{-1}(x, y) \times B_r^n(x, y) \times M_r(x, y) = D^n.$$

Letting $B_r(x, y) = (b_{ij})$, we have the following linear system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} b_{i1}\beta_1^r + b_{i2}\beta_1^{r-1} + \dots + b_{i(r+1)} = \beta_1^{n+r+1-i}, \\ b_{i1}\beta_2^r + b_{i2}\beta_2^{r-1} + \dots + b_{i(r+1)} = \beta_2^{n+r+1-i}, \\ \vdots \\ b_{i1}\beta_{r+1}^r + b_{i2}\beta_{r+1}^{r-1} + \dots + b_{i(r+1)} = \beta_{r+1}^{n+r+1-i}. \end{cases}$$

Thus, for each $1 \leq i, j \leq r$ we have

$$b_{ij} = \frac{\det(M_r^{(j)}(x, y))}{\det(M_r(x, y))},$$

where $(M_r^j(x, y))$ is the matrix obtained from $(M_r(x, y))$ by replacing the j^{th} column with the vector

$$M_r^i(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_1^{n+r+1-i} \\ \beta_2^{n+r+1-i} \\ \vdots \\ \beta_r^{n+r+1-i} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Setting $i = j = 1$, we get $b_{11} = U_{n+1}^{(-r)} = \frac{\det(M_r^1(x, y))}{\det(M_r(x, y))}$.

Finally, using Equation (8), we have

$$\begin{aligned} V_n^{(-r)} &= rU_{n+1}^{(-r)} - xy^{-1}U_{n-r}^{(-r)} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \frac{r\beta_k^{n+r+1} - xy^{-1}\beta_k^{n-r+r}}{r\beta_k^{r+1} - xy^{-1}} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \beta_k^n \frac{r\beta_k^{r+1} - xy^{-1}}{r\beta_k^{r+1} - xy^{-1}} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} \beta_k^n. \end{aligned}$$

□

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